

women were included in this study. They performed the regular physical activity program with vegetarian diets and were staying at the residential building together for a total of 10 days. Variables including body composition, physical fitness factors, POMS score, and blood BDNF level were measured twice before and after the intervention.

Results: Our program showed the beneficial effects of improvement of physical fitness and weight loss. Especially, the blood BDNF level was significantly increased in the both females ($t = -2.761, p = .013$) and male students after the intervention ($t = -3.392, p = .002$), respectively, suggesting the beneficial contribution of this intervention on the mental health of Korean collegiate students.

Conclusion: These data suggest that our program may be a useful tool for the mental and physical health improvement of Korean collegiate students. Further studies using larger sample sizes will be needed to replicate the health-benefit effect of this intervention.

Relationship Between Sport Participation Motivation and Teaching Games for Understanding Among Novice Handball Players

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The teaching games for understanding (TGfU) approach breaks games skills down into step-by-step movements

Effect of the TGfU Approach on Motor Development and Social Maturity of Elementary School Students

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The teaching games for understanding (TGfU) approach was developed to tap into children's inherent desire to play. If TGfU, as a new pedagogical model in physical education (PE), is to become a movement that will broaden the scope of PE, it must be anchored in sound research that explores its influences on different domains. Of significant importance in the delivery of learning opportunities within a TGfU structure is the notion that it has the potential to enhance development of psychomotor, cognitive, affective, and social skills. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of the TGfU approach in soccer on the motor and social development of Grade 4 elementary school students (10 years old) compared to the technique-based approach. Two Grade 4 classes (each 15 students) from an elementary school in Tehran City, Iran, were selected as the experimental and control groups. The experimental group was followed for 10 soccer units, which were taught using the TGfU approach in 5 weeks (2 sessions per week). At the same time, the control group was trained based on a traditional technique-based

approach. The Movement Assessment Battery for Children (2nd Edition) and the Vineland Social Maturity Scale were used to evaluate motor development and social maturity of participants, respectively. An analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistical method was used to confirm the results when there were significant differences at the baseline level (pretest score was used as a covariate). The ANCOVA results revealed a significant difference between the experimental and control groups in both motor development and social maturity variables ($p < .05$). The findings of this study showed that the experimental group that was taught with the TGfU approach had significant main effects in motor and social development compared with the group taught the traditional technique-based approach.

Effects of Dyad Training on Children's Learning of Front-Crawl Swimming

same experience in swimming were assigned to 2 groups of dyad or individual training. After receiving instructions and observing some perfect performances of the skill, 1 of each dyad entered the water and the other 1 stayed outside. The 1 outside (just like a coach) gave feedback to the partner after each trial. After some trials, they exchanged their roles. Children in the individual-training group all entered the water and simultaneously performed the skill after having gotten instructions and making perfect model observation. Thus, 50% of practice trials in the dyad group were physical and 50% were observational, while all of the practice trials in the individual group were physical. Practice trials were marked in a checklist by the instructor. Swimming lessons were facilitated in some way according to pedagogical principles of TGfU for both groups. All participants came back to the pool for a retention test 1 week after the end of the 8-session intervention. In the retention test, each child swam 10 m individually, and their performance was filmed for later analyses. Results showed that the